

New Marketing Approach to Enhance Brand Awareness: Case Study of an Electronic Retailer Company in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The object in this research is a consumer electronics retailer, one of the official resellers of Apple products in Indonesia. Currently, the company has three sales channels, one of which is through the Website. Based on observation and interviews with the business owner, it is known that the achievement through Website sales is the lowest compared to other channels. Besides data from similarweb, the company website traffic per month is only 112,000 visitors, which is lower than other competitors. The company has carried out several marketing strategies in general for all their channel, but it has not specifically on their online channels, especially for websites and O2O services. Therefore, this study aims to propose a new strategy to increase awareness for the consumer electronic retailer, especially for their websites and Online to Offline (O2O) services.

This study analyzes business problems using SWOT analysis. To measure brand awareness, the 5A's Model Analysis framework is used, then to measure brand awareness and O2O acceptance to customers, Omnichannel marketing analysis is used specifically for O2O. Data and information were obtained from various sources such as interviews with employees, questionnaires using convenience sampling, and observation. The study found that the lack of brand awareness caused the company not to optimize in using marketing channels. The customer experience in using the Website was still relatively low, the promotions carried out by competitors were more attractive, and generally, respondents still liked offline purchases. To overcome the problems faced, increase brand awareness for websites and O2O services this company owns. This research proposed solution using the RACE Framework as a marketing strategy.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness; Consumer Electronic Retailer; 5A's Model Analysis; Online to Offline; RACE Framework

1. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing internet penetration in Indonesia, which reaches 273 million people [2], Indonesia is one of the largest markets for consumer electronic products, especially gadgets, globally. The competition between gadgets or mobile devices retailers in Indonesia is getting tougher. In 2021, smartphone users in Indonesia reached 199 million people based on data. The high number of internet and smartphone users could be a big opportunity for mobile device companies to enter Indonesia. Currently, in Indonesia, there are more than ten brands of mobile devices. One of the brands is Apple. Apple is a multinational technology company based in the United States specializing in consumer electronics, software, and online services. Globally, especially for its smartphone products,

Apple generally always ranks in the top 2 from 2019 to 2021. However, this is different from what happened in the Indonesian market. In the last four years, from 2018-to 2021, Apple's market share in Indonesia was only 6.11% and was in the fifth position [9]. In Indonesia, Apple does not have its flagship store. They sell their product mainly through their authorized reseller.

Gimap is the youngest Apple reseller in Indonesia, which was just established at the end of 2019. From the beginning of its establishment until now, the COVID-19 pandemic has attacked Indonesia, affecting the economy, especially in the retail industry. Gimaps's business's young age and the COVID-19 pandemic have to face giant competitors whose brands are already attached to the public. This makes the competition between the retailer getting tougher and stronger. As we know, digitalization is an essential part of this retail industry to compete in the market. Thus, the company has taken a new step by providing online retail sales through the Website, with the hope of helping the business recover from the impact of the pandemic that has changed people's spending habits.

Table 1. Indonesia Apple's Authorized Reseller Website Traffic

	<i>PBox</i>	<i>Erisoace</i>	<i>Gimap</i>	<i>StoryP</i>
Monthly Average Visit	3.6 million	1.1 million	112 thousand	-
Total Visit in Dec '21	3.7 million	1.3 million	123 thousand	<50 thousand

However, brand awareness and sales through the Website are still low, and this can be seen from the fact that website traffic is also ten times lower than its competitors [8]. Besides that, the Website's sales are also the lowest compared to other channels such as Offline stores/brick and mortar and e-commerce. Another concern for the company's management is that many people do not know that GIMAP has an Online to Offline (O2O) sales feature.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

SWOT is a framework that enables a company to derive strategic implications by combining insights obtained from an internal analysis of the company's strengths and weaknesses with those obtained from an external analysis of opportunities and threats. A SWOT analysis must be carried out thoroughly to be an effective management tool. A SWOT analysis enables a strategic leader to assess a company's current situation and prospects by accounting for internal and external factors. The SWOT analysis encourages strategic leaders to scan their internal and external environments for relevant factors that may impact their current or future competitive advantage [7].

The five A's framework is a versatile tool that can be applied to any industry. When used to describe customer behaviour, it paints a more accurate picture of the customer's journey. It enables cross-industry comparisons, revealing insights into industry characteristics. It also provides information about a company's customer relationship compared to its competitors. When a company discovers, for example, that the most common path its customers frequently take differs significantly from the typical customer path in its industry, the company may discover either an authentic differentiation or a hidden customer experience problem. The 5A's consist of Aware, Appeal, Ask, Act and Advocate. During the aware phase, customers are passively exposed to many brands due to previous experience, marketing communications, and the advocacy of others. A customer who has previously encountered a brand will most likely be able to recall and recognize it. Other customers' word-of-mouth and company-driven advertising are also important sources of brand awareness. Customers process all of the messages they are exposed to during the Appeal phase, either creating short-term memory or amplifying long-term memory, and become attracted to a small number of brands [3].

During the asking stage, customers are typically prompted by their curiosity to research the brands actively; they are drawn to more information from friends and family, the media, and directly from the brands. Customers can ask their friends for recommendations or evaluate the shortlist themselves. They may look for online product reviews if they decide to do more research on some brands. Then, it is critical to remember that desired customer actions are not limited to purchases in the act phase. After purchasing it, customers engage with a brand more deeply through consumption and usage and post-purchase services. Brands must engage their customers and ensure positive and memorable ownership and user experience. Lastly, customers may develop a strong sense of brand loyalty overtime in the advocate phase, as evidenced by retention, repurchase, and, eventually, advocacy to others. Active advocates recommend brands they like without being asked. They become evangelists by telling others about their positive experiences [3].

Omnichannel integrates multiple channels to create a seamless and consistent customer experience. Channel silos must be broken down, and goals and strategies must be aligned. This will ensure a coordinated effort across multiple online and offline channels to entice customers to commit to a purchase. To effectively implement an omnichannel strategy, a company should focus on the most important touchpoints and channels and engage employees throughout the organization to support it [3]. O2O is an omnichannel strategy that creates a seamless online purchasing experience for customers. **O2O retail**, also known as online-to-offline retail, is a strategy that encourages consumers to make in-store purchases after beginning their shopping journeys online. By combining online and offline capabilities, O2O strategies maximize consumer convenience and flexibility, increasing sales and brand loyalty [5].

RACE Marketing Planning Model provides a simple framework for businesses to develop a digital marketing or omnichannel communications strategy that addresses the challenges of reaching and engaging online audiences to prompt conversion to online

or offline sales. The RACE framework can also be used to develop a strategy for increasing brand awareness and retaining customers. This framework will also aid in integrating digital and traditional marketing activities. RACE is a set of four steps or online marketing activities designed to assist brands in engaging their customers throughout the customer lifecycle, which are as follows: Reach, Act, Convert, and Engage. Reach aims to increase brand awareness and visibility on other websites and offline media to increase traffic by driving visitors to sites. Act's next goal is to generate online leads that can be nurtured along the 'path-to-purchase.' Then, for convert, the goal is to convert to a sale, either online or offline, because RACE is a multichannel or omnichannel marketing framework. Finally, engagement establishes a long-term relationship with existing customers to foster customer loyalty, repeat purchases, and increase customer lifetime value [1].

3. METHODOLOGY

The researcher will employ various qualitative and quantitative methods to achieve the research objective. The qualitative research method collects interpretations to comprehend the company's business overview. The research gathers data from primary and secondary sources. For the qualitative method, the primary data obtained from the in-depth interview with the head of marketing and the E-commerce supervisor of the company and the observations made during the interview will be used. The primary data was obtained from a questionnaire with respondents who have ever purchased a gadget and are at least 18 years old for the quantitative method. Then the secondary data are gathered from internal company data, websites, books, articles, and other media. SWOT and the thematic framework will analyze all of the data. The results of each framework's analysis will be summarized in a fishbone diagram that explains the root cause of the problem. For the strategy will be formulated in the RACE Framework.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. SWOT

1) Internal Analysis: Strength and Weakness

Internal analysis is looking inside a company to analyze its resources, capabilities, and core competencies to understand its strengths and weaknesses [7]. Based on the internal analysis, the following points will be explained regarding Gimap's strengths and weaknesses:

a) Strength of Gimap

- Gimap is a subsidiary of the largest retailer in Indonesia. As a subsidiary of this giant retailer, it is one of the Gimap strengths. With a parent's company big name and good reputation, Gimap can be viewed favourably by its partners and consumers.
- CAP provides a complete and integrated ecosystem as the parent company. The existence of CAPCLUB Points as a loyalty reward for the customer can be a strength for Gimap because for every purchase, you will get points, and customers can redeem these points at Gimap and other retailers associated with CAP.
- Gimap status as Apple's Authorized Reseller and Apple's Premium Reseller can increase customer confidence in purchasing the product. In addition, Gimap also has a product warranty for one year; its service centre works with Apple and partner's service centres spread across Indonesia.
- For sales through the Website, Gimap collaborates with many partners such as trusted third-party logistics (3PL) to provide insurance services during shipping specifically for product devices.
- Gimap becomes product quality by providing exchange services for every customer who purchases a product and receives a damaged product when they just received it. Product return claims are valid 1x24 hours after the customer receives the product and will be replaced with a new product.

b) Weakness of Gimap

- Gimap is new in the market and just started operating in November 2019, compared to competitors already established for more than 5-years.
- The user interface and user experience of the Gimap website are still not performing well. For example, the user interface in the mobile view is not balanced and not optimized yet.
- The limited payment method available for purchases on the Website now only accepts payments via credit cards, debit cards and bank transfers.

- Gimap has not optimized the marketing channel that they own
- Many receive complaints about the Gimap website because the Website's performance is not running well. For example, it can cause backorders or customers cannot pay for the product due to an error on the Website. Based on internal data, in November 2021, there were 55 backorder transactions. In December 2021, there were eight transactions in January & February 2022, and there were ten transactions. Besides that, there are also complaints about GIMAP, especially the Website through social media.

2) *External Analysis: Opportunities and Threats*

External analysis analyzes factors outside the firm that can affect its ability to gain and maintain a competitive advantage. [7]. Based on the external analysis, the following points will be explained regarding Gimap's Opportunities and threats:

a) *Opportunities*

- Through the Ministry of Industry, as of 18 April 2020, the government has officially implemented the rules for controlling the International Mobile Equipment Identity (IMEI). This regulation will prohibit the trade of illegal mobile phones in Indonesia and encourage GIMAP to gain more sales because customers cannot buy Apple's Products from abroad or "BM" products.
- Due to the rapid development of technology and digitalization, according to statista.com, as of 2021 there are 201 million Internet users in Indonesia. If compared to the whole population in Indonesia that around 273 million [2]. 73% of the population already use the Internet, but only 8% of the population ever purchase the gadget online. This can be the opportunity for GIMAP to penetrate its product through an online channel such as a Website.
- b) *Threat*
- Based on Deloitte Consumer Insight in 2021, since the Covid-19 Pandemic attacked Indonesia, the behaviour of Indonesian customers towards consumer electronics has changed slightly. Now customers prioritize gadgets' quality, durability, and convenience compared to design, technology, and after-sales, so it has become a challenge for GIMAP to recover from the conditions during the pandemic.
- For consumer electronic products, in this case, gadgets, customers want to see and feel the device directly. In addition, customers generally fear making online purchases outside of well-known e-commerce platforms. According to statista.com, most of Indonesia's consumers prefer to purchase mobile phones and gadgets through modern trade (e.g., supermarkets, department stores and speciality stores) rather than through e-commerce or Online [4]. Thus, the customer's sense of trust in purchases on the Website is lower
- Competitors that are already well-known offer better prices, promotions and processes. The competitor analysis shows that most competitors can interpret customer pain points and change them into features.

B. The Five A's Framework

To analyze the following framework, the data obtained from the distribution of the questionnaire was used. Ninety-four respondents meet the criteria of 18 years old and have purchased Apple products independently.

1) *Aware Approach*

To know about the customer's awareness of GIMAP, several questions are asked to the respondent. Based on the figure above, respondents know GIMAP as a retailer. In the questionnaire, 84% know GIMAP as a retailer that sells Apple devices and accessories, and 54% know that GIMAP has a Website to purchase the product online. The remaining 46% of respondents did not know that GIMAP has a Website. From the interview with Gimap's internal, they agree that many people know GIMAP as an official retailer in Indonesia, but few know that GIMAP has a website. One reason for this is that when the Website was launched, there was no special campaign to increase its awareness, so there was low brand assistance and awareness.

Table 2. Awareness to Brand

<i>Question</i>	<i>Answer</i>
Do you Know Gimap	84% Yes, 16% No
Do you know Gimap has a Website to purchase Apple's Products?	54% Yes; 46% No

Furthermore, from the Website's marketing channel traffic [8]. According to the table, Gimap has not optimized their referrals, social, mail, and display since the distribution from those channels is relatively low. According to the same source, the insight for social traffic leading to Gimap's Website reveals that Gimap has not yet focused and optimized its social media channels, particularly Instagram and Facebook.

Table 3. Marketing Channel Distribution

	<i>Direct</i>	<i>Referrals</i>	<i>Search</i>	<i>Social</i>	<i>Mail</i>	<i>Display</i>
<i>Distribution</i>	36.25%	0.5%	59.85%	1.9%	0%	1.51%

Table 4. Social Media Distribution

	<i>Youtube</i>	<i>Twitter</i>	<i>Facebook</i>	<i>Instagram</i>
<i>Distribution</i>	55.27%	28.54%	14.5%	1.68%

2) Appeal Approach

To determine what factors influence customer appeal, a question about what information customers require is posed to them. The first question is whether the respondent has ever used GIMAP's social media; 52% of respondents never used GIMAP's social media. Only 48% visit GIMAP's social media to learn more about products, promotions, and other topics. This questionnaire can be said to fit the conditions that occur because when viewed from social media followers such as GIMAP's Instagram, which is still low, around 196 thousand users with a 0.2 percent engagement rate [6]. Compared to competitors like PBox, the number of followers is 1.079 million.

According to the survey results, in order to increase attractiveness, the majority of respondents want various information on the Website such as 36 % want to know the availability of promos on the GIMAP website, 31 % want to know detailed descriptions and specifications, 18% want to know the amount of stock, 10% want to see the review from the previous purchase, and the remain want to know the delivery detail and time.

3) Ask Approach

To understand the asking phase from the customer's perspective, the question asked about the most important factors customers consider when buying Apple products on the GIMAP website and whom they consult for advice. The results show that assurance of product authenticity is an important factor influencing 30.9 % of respondents to purchase Apple's Products. Price and promotion impact 24.5% and 23.4 % of respondents, respectively.

In the electronic customer retail industry, particularly gadgets, the majority of respondents, 61 %, are influenced to make purchases by tech experts. Only 16% and 14% of respondents believe that the popularity of Instagram and YouTube influencers can persuade them to buy gadgets, respectively. This is in stark contrast to what happened in GIMAP, where most KOLs are Instagram Influencers who focus on lifestyle rather than gadgets.

4) Act Approach

In this stage, the respondent will represent whether they have ever visited or purchased from the GIMAP website and whether they are interested in purchasing from the GIMAP website. It is known that the majority of respondents, up to 89 %, have never made a purchase through the Website, and only 11 % have ever made a purchase through Gimap's Website. This is consistent with information obtained from the e-commerce supervisor, who stated that GIMAP website sales were low compared to other channels such as Offline stores and Shopee.

Table 5. Act Approach

<i>Question</i>	<i>Answer</i>
Have you ever purchased at Gimap's Website	12% Yes, 89% No
Do you interested in purchasing at Gimap's Website?	77% Yes; 23% No

After reading a brief description of GIMAP and its Website, respondents were asked whether they were interested in using the GIMAP website. 77% of respondents said yes, they are interested in using the Website, while 23% said no. The majority of respondents are eager to visit the GIMAP website. This indicates that after learning more about GIMAP, particularly its Website, respondents are eager to make a purchase.

5) Advocate Approach

For this section, respondents will answer a few questions about advocates, such as whether they would be willing to recommend their purchasing experience if they had purchased their product and through what channel they would convey the recommendation. The first question asks if the respondent is willing to recommend the Gimap website to family and friends. Most of the respondents (82%) will recommend GIMAP's Website to their relatives, while 18% are unwilling to make any recommendation to their relatives.

Table 6. Advocate Approach

Question	Answer
Do you willing to recommend the Website to your relatives	82% Yes, 18% No

Next question show what channel the respondents choose to review their experience. The majority of respondents conveniently share their experience through Word of Mouth; 31% will share their experience on social media, while 21% will share their experience in the comment section of E-commerce, and 11% of respondents would leave a review on Google. The remaining 3% would share their experience on a platform review site like gadgetreview.com.

Table 7. Channel to Review

	WoM	Social Media	Comment Section at E-Commerce	Google Review	Platform review (gadgetreview.com, etc)
Percentage	33%	31%	21%	11%	3%

So far, Gimap teams' have implemented social media and the e-commerce comment section as advocacy media. For example, the GIMAP social media team will repost to customers who review the product and purchase process at GIMAP. The Shopee customer service team will actively serve and respond to various customer reviews in the comment section of each SKU.

C. Omnichannel Marketing (O2O Analysis)

For the time being, GIMAP is attempting to integrate its omnichannel strategy through O2O Retail Services. This is consistent with GIMAP's parent company, CAP's, goal of becoming Indonesia's leading omnichannel retailer. The offline and online selling channels complement rather than compete with one another. According to the interview with the Gimap Team, the Omnichannel strategy implemented by GIMAP in the form of O2O is still in its early stages, with customers only being able to buy through the Website and pick up products at offline stores/brick and mortar (Pick-up at Store). This service is still in its early stages, having been launched by GIMAP in October 2021 and then deactivated due to enhancements. The following analysis will obtain responses from respondents regarding their knowledge and interest in O2O.

Table 8. O2O Analysis

Question	Answer
Do you know that Gimap has O2O Services	64% Yes, 36% No
Do you willing to purchase Apple's product using O2O Services?	78% Yes; 22% No

The first question concerns respondents' knowledge of O2O, specifically whether they are aware of the O2O services offered by the GIMAP Website. The vast majority of respondents, 64%, were unaware of the existence of this service. Based on observations and

interviews with internal team members, GIMAP does not have a special campaign or promotion to raise awareness of this O2O. This could be why many respondents are unaware of this service. After reading a brief description of O2O services, 78% of respondents are willing and interested in purchasing via the service. The following are some of the reasons respondents are interested in O2O services.

Table 9. Respondent's reason

	<i>You can see the product directly</i>	<i>Increase their confidence & trust</i>	<i>Can consult with Apple's Master in Store</i>
<i>Percentage</i>	45%	29%	26%

Following that, respondents were asked what additional features they assume are required to improve O2O performance. According to most respondents (53%), GIMAP should provide real-time customer service to assist customers in purchasing O2O. Then, 31% of respondents suggest that GIMAP provides data on each product's available stock in each store to improve the O2O service. According to 15% of respondents, GIMAP should provide a procedure for purchasing and picking up the product if the customer chooses O2O Service.

Table 10. Respondent's suggestion of a feature

	<i>Realtime Customer Service</i>	<i>Information about remaining stocks</i>	<i>Information about purchase procedure</i>	<i>Information about how to claim warranty & Services</i>
<i>Percentage</i>	53%	31%	15%	1%

D. Root Cause Analysis

Based on the analysis of business issues and the results of the questionnaire, it has been determined that the causes of low GIMAP website traffic and sales that are not as good as other GIMAP channels are: From the perspective of an Apple user, the majority of respondents (around 96 percent) are aware of GIMAP as an Apple Official retailer via brick-and-mortar stores / offline stores, but nearly half are unaware that GIMAP has their Website to purchase Apple's products and the O2O service that is provided. They prefer to buy offline because they can check the product's availability and increase their trust in the product. Respondents in this digital era typically see advertisements through digital channels such as social media, search engines, and email. However, based on the above analysis, it was discovered that traffic from social media, email, and display ads is still very low, falling below 3% for each. This shows that GIMAP was unable to optimize its marketing channel. The marketing channel can be used to share information that GIMAP already has on its Website and O2O features.

Furthermore, based on the competitor analysis in this chapter, it was discovered that competitors could provide a better customer experience by having features that support their sales on their Website and a website that is easy to use and consistent when accessed on desktop or mobile. Based on interviews and observations with GIMAP internals, they also admit that they have historically undervalued customer experience. Finally, from the standpoint of competitors, competitors have the advantage of having grown into large players capable of competing at more attractive prices and promotions.

Figure 1. Fishbone Diagram

E. Proposed RACE Framework

To increase awareness of GIMAP and O2O websites, this study proposes a digital marketing strategy using the RACE Framework for GIMAP, which is referred to as follows in the table below. Each proposed solution will be categorized according to each phase of the RACE framework. For the reach stage, there are four proposals, namely Display Ads, Content Marketing, SEO and Influencer Outreach. Then, there are two proposals for the act stage, namely social media marketing and email marketing. For the convert phase, there are five proposals, namely personalized email, referral program, testimonial & review column, live chat, and a cross-selling strategy. Finally, there are three proposals in the engage phase: enhancing customer experience when using the Website, tiered loyalty program, and re-engaging email program.

Table 11. Proposed RACE Framework as Solution

No	RACE Framework	Digital Marketing Strategy	Conclusion
1	Reach	Display Ads	Create interactive, attractive, high-quality visuals that can be placed all over the Internet (Blog, News site, CAP's Website, Gadget review site, search engine, etc.). Once the display is clicked, it will redirect to GIMAP's Website, where the visitor can search and purchase the product.
2	Reach	Content Marketing	Create content in enticing messages, static images and videos about how to purchase using O2O service, maximize the device, etc., to enhance customers' knowledge about GIMAP and the products.
3	Reach	Search Engine Optimization	Make GIMAP's Website become the first Website to appear on search engines when searching for Apple Products in Indonesia. So that it can increase traffic to the GIMAP's Website. It can be done by using the right keyword that can describe GIMAP

4	Reach	Influencer Outreach	Collaborate with influencers, especially tech reviews and Instagram influencers who have many followers on their accounts and high engagement rates. Influencers can promote purchases through the GIMAP website and share their experiences when making purchases. Besides that, Influencers can promote by sharing their KOL Code to attract their followers to purchase, which leads to conversion.
5	Act	Social Media Marketing	Create quizzes and giveaways on GIMAP's social media to engage with the followers and increase visibility. Then, GIMAP can create social media takeover with the Influencer, update the activities and events to gain interaction with the followers and reduce the communication gap.
6	Act	Email Marketing	GIMAP can provide promotions for each new email subscriber as a first welcome email strategy. In addition, Email marketing is useful for informing stock availability and upcoming events. To increase the subscriber, GIMAP can put up Up Banner if visitors visit the Website.
7	Convert	Personalized Email	GIMAP can bring personal email to the customer that already subscribes to GIMAP's newsletter at the Website with a personalized email. Personalized email content could be a special promotion on a birthday or use the O2O services, info the device's anniversary, or send a special invitation to attend GIMAP's event.
8	Convert	Referral Program	The program is eligible for the existing customer as a referrer to invite their relatives as referees to purchase the product at GIMAP's Website. If the referee purchases the product, they will receive a special promo, and the referrer will get an additional CAPCLUB Point. This program could be in the form of a unique code or campaign on social media.
9	Convert	Testimonial & Review Column	The testimonial & review column will be placed on the product display page (PDP) of the GIMAP's Website. This can help customers increase their trust and know the performance of GIMAP. In addition, a review column on the Website that is integrated with Google Reviews will increase traffic that redirects to GIMAP's Website
10	Convert	Live Chat	Live chat with GIMAP customer service aims to allow customers to interact to ask about product info, how to purchase, complain, and others. With live chat, customers
	RACE	Digital	Conclusion
No	Framework	Marketing	
		Strategy	
			can avoid failing to make purchases due to a lack of information and slow response from the GIMAP team.
11	Convert	Cross-Selling Strategy	The cross-selling strategy that GIMAP can do is bundling both with gadget insurance companies and telecommunications operators. This can increase GIMAP's sales volume.

12	Engage	Enhance Customer Experience	Improved customer experience in the form of improving the UI/UX of the Website, synchronizing the appearance of the Website in web view and mobile view so that customers can easily use it, adding same-day or instant delivery options by collaborating with ride-hail companies, and finally adding payment methods to facilitate customer payments that located throughout Indonesia by a partnership with E-Wallet companies and multi-finance companies. In addition, GIMAP can also inform stock availability on its Website to improve customer experience, especially for O2O customers.
13	Engage	Tiered Loyalty Program	Enhance the function of CAPCLUB Points by working with the CAP team to create a tiered loyalty program. This tiered loyalty program will categorize each member based on their spending. Each category will receive different benefits, thus spurring customers to increase purchases on the GIMAP website.
14	Engage	Re-Engage Email Program	Re-engage emails can be information on the release date for new products, special access to purchase these new products and informing when the warranty period expires. Those actions can remind the customer to visit and purchase at GIMAP's Website.

5. CONCLUSION

After conducting a thorough analysis, it was discovered that the root cause of GIMAP's low brand awareness is that many people are still unaware of the GIMAP website, as well as the O2O services, which is due to GIMAP being less than optimal in using the marketing channels they have, such as not optimizing their social media, direct, and email. Then there are unappealing promotions, as GIMAP's promotions are still very general, with no targeting for specific types of customers. Aside from that, the experience of using a website that is not customer-centric or user-friendly, even though these are important factors influencing customer purchase decisions. Furthermore, customers prefer to buy products offline because they have more confidence and trust in quality, among other things. So, in order to address the root cause, the research must provide the appropriate marketing strategy as a solution to improve GIMAP's Website and O2O by utilizing the RACE Framework.

Based on the RACE Framework, GIMAP can set display ads on various sites related to gadgets, lifestyle, and consumer electronics; optimize search engine optimization; create interactive content marketing, and invite influencers to share their experience using Website and O2O services. Then, in the Act phase, GIMAP can begin working with their social media platform by creating a quiz, giveaway, or live program, and then optimize their email marketing by giving new newsletter subscribers a promotion. GIMAP can use a referral program, create a review column on their Website, offer /live chat, cross-selling, and send personalized emails to their newsletter subscribers during the Convert Phase. Finally, during the engage phase, GIMAP must improve the customer experience by improving the Website's capabilities, updating the existing loyalty program (CAPClub) to become a tiered loyalty program, and developing a re-engage email program to remind them about their previous purchases at GIMAP.

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